

Contextual analysis of citations using rule-based approaches: “The best soups are made in old pots”

Marc Bertin¹ and Iana Atanassova²

¹*marc.bertin@univ-lyon1.fr*

ELICO Laboratory, Claude Bernard Lyon 1 University, (France)

²*iana.atanassova@univ-fcomte.fr*

Université de Franche-Comté, CRIT, F-25000 Besançon, (France)
Institut Universitaire de France (IUF), (France)

Abstract

In this paper, we present an experiment on annotating citation contexts using a rule-based approach to investigate the extent of text around citations. The study of citation contexts and their types has been a central issue in recent work on citations. We processed articles from seven PLOS journals and performed semantic annotation of citation contexts based on linguistic resources we constructed. We built on previous work on verb form analysis, n-grams, and semantic category modeling in the form of a linguistic ontology. Based on the observations obtained, we propose some directions of work for the constitution of a semantically annotated corpus. The intermediate results obtained lead us to formulate hypotheses between the IMRaD structure and certain semantic categories.

Introduction

Understanding citations in their context is an unsolved problem in information science. However, this central question of bibliometric activity, long studied by bibliometricians and other epistemologists, whether on the linguistic, sociological, or symbolic level, is still relevant today. As Cronin (1981) noted, bibliometricians are still searching for a theory of citation, and the work of Tahamtan & Bornmann (2022), which proposes SSCT (Social Systems Citation Theory) is an important step in this direction.

The study of citation contexts is more than ever at the center of scientific debate, and the need for a theory of citation becomes essential. The study of the relationships between references in the text is an important step in the semantic modeling and annotation of these relationships. On the one hand, the work of Tahamtan & Bornmann (2022) shows a deep social and psychological dimension. On the other hand, deep learning also wants to make its contribution. The recent unfortunate experience of Galactica shows this potential in terms of scientific information retrieval. According to the work of Taylor et al. (2022), of which the article cited here is a preprint, information overload is a major obstacle to scientific progress. To this end, they trained their model on a large scientific corpus consisting of articles, reference material, knowledge bases, and many other sources. The latter trained a model on a corpus of more than 360 million citation contexts. It also indexed over 50 million bibliographic references. The authors of this paper believe that these results demonstrate the potential of language models as a new interface for science. The trivial hypothesis announced is that citations can help discover new publications.

A sociological, psychological, and ethical difficulty leads us to consider another possibility. Indeed, the nature of the data to be studied must lead us to produce analyses and datasets based on principles of comprehensibility and reproducibility. To this end, we develop a method that allows semantic annotation of rule-based corpora. This type of approach is less used today because it suffers from two major limitations: the low recall rate and the mobilization of experts. However, two important qualities have been identified. The high precision in the context of

semantic annotation on the one hand, and on the other hand, the underlying understanding that this work brings to the studied phenomenon.

Understanding the citation acts is a necessary step to categorize the semantic relationships between research papers. To this end, the study of the full text of articles can provide relevant empirical results. This is an essential step, and the Open Access and Open Science movements are contributing to the development of such approaches. Access to the full text of articles is an essential step for populating ontologies from the Semantic Web. In this perspective, Peroni & Shotton (2012) have already proposed an ontological modeling of bibliographic references.

Related work

The study of text is naturally complex due to the nature of language, and the methods used are diverse and varied. Maričić (1998) attaches importance to the citations that are present in the methods section or in the results section. Bornmann & Daniel (2008) proposed a citation content analysis of articles with low and high citation counts. Liu et al. (2013) use full-text citation analysis along with supervised topic modeling and network analysis algorithms to improve classical bibliometric analysis. Bertin et al. (2016) show a form of invariance in the IMRaD structure. Boyack, et al. (2018) have analyzed the in-text citations of over five million articles from two large databases - the PubMed Central Open Access Subset and Elsevier journals. Saier and Färber (2020) propose a large scientific dataset with annotated in-text citations. Shahid (2021) proposed an approach based on three citation models (1) bibliographic linkage, (2) co-citation, and (3) direct citation to provide a better approach to information retrieval and improve recommendation systems.

Methodology

If the complexity of this research topic requires a transdisciplinary dialogue involving not only bibliometricians but also linguists, sociologists and computer scientists, a semantic approach will provide a first insight into the semantic dimension of citation acts. This will contribute to a transdisciplinary dialogue that will lead to the proposal of a conceptual model of citation acts and the development of a prototype for identification, extraction and classification. Our goal is to develop a typology of citation contexts in order to better explain citation acts and to establish the functional basis of their use. This work is a continuation of previous work on textual analysis of citation contexts in scientific publications in PLOS. We have based our work on the linguistic ontology proposed by Bertin and Atanassova (2009). It was implemented on a multilingual corpus (French-English) to underline the multilingual aspect of this approach. We have also relied on the work of Bertin, M. and Atanassova, I. (2014), which proposes a study of the verbs present in the contexts of citations. It was shown that the knowledge of a part of the verbs of a given language is sufficient to analyze a large part of the citation contexts. So our problem is this: can we build linguistic resources from the most common verbs? This will allow us to have sufficient linguistic knowledge to define semantic labels that are consistent with the linguistic ontology. For this, we will also mobilize the linguistic knowledge produced by Bertin, et al. Lariviere (2016) to build linguistic resources.

We propose to associate a context with a bibliographic reference. The bibliographic references are then considered as indicators. The linguistic indices, on the other hand, allow us to determine specific semantic information, to reduce indeterminacy and to specify the quality of the reference. They are the only knowledge we need to determine the categories and they are present around the indicator, in the same textual segment as the indicator. The method of Contextual Exploration developed by Desclés (1981; 1997) makes it possible with the help of indices to eliminate the semantic indeterminacy of the linguistic unit analyzed and to propose a qualitative categorization of bibliographic references. The occurrences of the indicator

determine which text segments need to be processed for the accomplishment of this task. In this study, we consider that this text segment coincides with the sentence. We reserve the possibility of extending our research to larger text spans, as the theory allows, if it should prove necessary to eliminate some ambiguities. Once the context has been determined, we need to consider the position of the index in relation to the indicator.

Table 1 presents the semantic categories of the acts of citation. We implement the identification of these categories using rule-based approach.

Table 1. Semantic Category of Citation Acts

Act of Citation	Definition	
	Appreciation	Agreement
		Disagreement
	Information	Hypothesis
		Result
		Method
		Citation
	Comparison	Similarity
		Difference
	Point of view	Position

In this work, we have used the same corpus as in the previous studies. Indeed, this corpus is available and many works refer to it. From a quantitative point of view, it contains 1,815,428 citation contexts which will be treated from a semantic point of view in order to produce a first representation of their semantic dimension. The corpus covers 7 PLOS journals and selected only scientific articles. For the analysis produced, we retained only the sections in the IMRaD structure.

Results

The application of the proposed method allows us to accurately describe some of the citation contexts by showing their semantic richness. In the examples below, the extracted sentences show the discourse categories identified by our implementation.

1 – disagreement - In part, our findings contradict early studies of dispersal mode and spatial pattern performed by Hubbell [4].

2- agreement - These results agree with our previous Monte-Carlo simulation results for the HIV-1 Tat circuit [34] as well as other groups' findings [4,5].

3 – disagreement - This appears to disagree with Park and Priess, who showed that sister pairs of 16-AB and 32-AB cell stage AB blastomeres display an asymmetric expression of POP-1, although they never touched P2 or its descendants [19].

The three sentences below each show a semantic category related to agreement and another related to disagreement. A limitation of our study is that we have not yet studied negative

citations in the same depth as the work of Bordignon (2020), Catalini (2015) and Bertin (2016). Table 2 presents the results obtained. It presents the semantic categories of the linguistic ontology identified in the PLOS corpus. This represents about 13% of the corpus that has been semantically annotated. This result is explained on the one hand by the fact that the citations may be superficial in nature and do not provide the semantics to define the nature of the relationship. In the context of this study, there is an intrinsic limitation of this intermediate result, which is the constitution of the resources. This is an important aspect that requires human resources to produce a quality resource.

Table 2. Semantic category and number of annotations obtained on the PLOS corpus

categories	Introduction	Method	Result	Discussion	Total
agreement	146	130	1868	3063	5207
comparison	1	1		1	3
definition	4665	5790	2984	3081	16520
difference	147	46	57	216	466
disagreement	911	262	892	2949	5014
hypothesis	12782	1223	6397	21130	41532
method	1178	5001	4063	1211	11453
position	292	33	120	809	1254
result	19648	29833	17257	42378	109116
similarity	7366	3903	16405	27747	55421
Total	47136	46222	50043	102585	245986

Figures 1 and 2 below show the radar results for six of the seven PLOS journals. We did not retain PLOS One, which is multidisciplinary. Figure 1 shows variations in the distribution of semantic categories according to the IMRaD structure. Figure 2 shows the distribution according to the different journals, showing relatively similar shapes for the 6 journals.

Figure 1. Distribution of the semantic categories in the IMRaD Structure

Figure 2. Distribution of the semantic categories in the PLOS journals

Concluding discussion, limitations, and perspective

The resulting table shows 10 of the 14 categories proposed in the linguistic ontology. At this stage, it is not possible to draw conclusions about the distribution of semantic annotations. However, some observations can be made. The semantic category disagreement is very present in the discussion part, while the category agreement is present in the discussion part, but also results. The categories definition, hypothesis and result are most present in the discussion part. Two hypotheses emerge and will be addressed later in a complementary study. 1 - Does the use and distribution of semantic categories vary across disciplines? 2 - Do semantic categories depend on a rhetorical structure? The PLOS journals involved have very similar topics. Therefore, the production of a new corpus will be necessary to produce a discussion about the categories in a disciplinary context.

The first point is that this work is an essential step to show that our approach can handle larger datasets with a scientific discourse analysis constraint based on linguistic approaches. The second point is the ability to capture relatively rare relationships. And this rarity should not be neglected. For example, the study of negative citation is a topic that is being addressed today and contributes to a better understanding of citation acts. The third point is the possibility of designing a standard corpus for deep learning purposes. This aspect deserves further discussion. The method proposed in this paper will allow us to propose a new dataset with the semantic annotations coming from the produced linguistic resources. This dataset will be available on Zenodo and will be freely accessible. The limitation of this ongoing study covers two aspects, which concern the coverage of linguistic resources and the evaluation of a category of discourse in the framework of an automated semantic annotation. The last point is the most sensitive and will require the implementation of Cohen's kappa coefficient, a statistic used to measure inter-rater reliability for given categories.

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